

Performance and Emission Analysis of a Variable Compression Ratio Diesel Engine Fueled with Hibiscus Cocos Nucifera Biodiesel Blend

Alapati Babji^{1*}, Yarrapragada KSS Rao², E. Nirmala Devi³, D. Santha Rao⁴

^{1,3}Department of Mechanical Engineering, Godavari Global University(GGU), Rajamahendravaram-533296, Andhra Pradesh, India.

²Department of Mechanical Engineering, Aditya University, Surampalem-533437, Andhra Pradesh, India.

⁴Mechanical Engineering Department, Visakha Institute of Engineering & Technology, Visakhapatnam-530027, Andhra Pradesh, India

*Corresponding author : Alapati Babji

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ABSTRACT

The fossil fuel reserves will be depleted soon. Diesel is used as a fuel in engines, resulting in poor combustion efficiency and more pollutants. Biodiesel is a promising alternate fuel for engines. Biodiesel derived from hibiscus cocos nucifera (HCN) oil is being used as a substitute fuel in a variable compression ratio diesel engine to improve efficiency and reduce emissions. The engine runs under various loads at 1500 rpm. The experiments are conducted on a VCR diesel engine using the biodiesel blend B25 at various compression ratios (CR15, CR16, CR17, and CR18), and the findings are compared to diesel fuel at a standard compression ratio of 17:1 in maximum load load. The performance characteristics of brake thermal efficiency improved by 5.14%, brake specific fuel consumption decreased by 5.71%, the emission characteristics of hydrocarbon decreased by 20.68%, carbon dioxide increased by 19.51%, smoke opacity decreased by 54.38%, and the combustion characteristic cylinder pressure increased by 4.05%. Cumulative heat release improved by 1.04%, net heat release decreased by 0.36%, and the mean gas temperature decreased by 0.56% at CR18. The findings show that the blend B25 can be applied as an alternate fuel for diesel engines without changes to the engine.

Keywords: Diesel; biodiesel; performance; emission; combustion; hibiscus cocos nucifera oil.

1. Introduction

The global population is growing, and energy consumption is skyrocketing, but fossil fuel reserves are depleting by the day, forcing renewable energy to step in to meet the energy demand. Fossil fuels produce greenhouse gases during combustion, which cause air pollution and global warming [1]. Renewable energy is green energy obtained from natural sources like solar energy, hydro energy, bioenergy, etc., that is not exhausted and is not harmful to humans. Nanofluids have gained popularity for their use in renewable energy systems [2]. [3] examined the diesel engine performance of pyrolysis oil as biodiesel made from waste tyre and cerium oxide. BTE increased by 2.85% for the B05 blend with 100 ppm cerium oxide at full load and emissions of hydrocarbons, smoke and carbon dioxide decreased by 7.7%, 3% and 1.33, respectively compared with diesel fuel. The cylinder pressure (CP) increased when compared with diesel for the B05 blend with 100 ppm cerium oxide due to catalytic activity in the combustion. [4] made biodiesel from Croton macrostachyus kernel oil. The RSM was used to optimise the synthesis process by varying reaction time, molar ratio, and catalyst loading. The biodiesel was mixed with diesel at 5%, 10%, 15% and 20% to find out the emissions and performance of a diesel engine. BTE is reduced, the BSFC is larger, and the exhaust gas temperature also improved as compared with diesel. Similarly, by using manufactured biodiesel blends, emissions are lowered. [5] studied the impact of load and compression ratio on first second and third generation ((karanja , jatropha, spirulina) biofuels in diesel engine to find out the piston force, soot formation, spray tip penetration and sauter mean diameter. At CR17.5, soot emissions decrease by 6.1%, 25.9%, and 5.59% for Karanja, Jatropha, and Spirulina, but increase as the compression ratio increases. [6] studied the biodiesel production from non-edible oils and VCR diesel engine performance by using multiple fuels. Fuel efficiency improved, fuel

consumption lowered by 30%, pollutants were reduced, and cylinder pressure was better managed. [7] conducted tests on a VCR CI engine at 1500 rpm speed by using rapeseed and mahua biodiesel at different blends and loads. Brake thermal efficiency decreased by 2.79%, and emissions of CO (20.66%) and HC (8.56%) decreased for blend BL20. [8] investigated the performance of diesel engine used for automobiles by using biodiesel (B100). The engine is operating at different compression ratios, ranging from 19 to 21. Compression ratio 21 gives better engine performance. [9] used microalgae biodiesel B20 blend on a VCR diesel engine to enhance performance and minimise the emissions. No significant variation is observed in performance compared with diesel. [10] examined the performance of hibiscus-coconut biodiesel blends on a diesel engine at a compression ratio (CR) of 17.5:1 at different loads. BP and BTE improved by 1.78% and 2.48% at full load, and blend B15 and emissions decreased. [11] conducted tests on a VCR diesel engine using 20%, 30%, and 40% of cotton seed oil blends at compression ratios of 18 to 22 and varying the loads. BSFC lowered to 0.290%, and BTE improved to 0.72%. [12] studied mahua and Ceiba pentandra combination biodiesel blends of 10 to 40% on CI engine at compression ratios from 15 to 19. Better results were obtained at CR18 for B20 blend at peak load of the engine. [13] used the RSM technique for optimization of the diesel engine parameters. The engine was powered by HCN biodiesel in a variety of compression ratios and blends. The B30 blend at CR15 gave better results. [14] studied the influence of combustion in combustion chamber design by using hydrogen and diesel. Experiments are conducted on two combustion chambers (original and manufactured) at 1850 rpm, different loads, and at different hydrogen injection timings. The original combustion chamber produced results as cylinder pressure increased by 1.41%. Energy consumption and particulate emissions decreased by 2.29% and 8.82% at 9 Nm load and with 12% hydrogen energy. [15] examined the combustion in a VCR diesel engine by using Nahar biodiesel blends (B05 to B50). Blend B40 gives the better performance. A maximum cylinder pressure of 70.91 bar was obtained for B100 at full load. [16] examined the impact of exhaust gas recirculation (EGR) on engine performance. At 20% EGR with low heat rejection (LHR) and karanja methyl ester, BSFC and No_x were reduced. [17] used pongamia and jatropa, each 5% to 20% biodiesel, in a diesel engine to estimate the size of the carbon particles. The size of carbon particles increases with load and blend ratio. The carbon particle size for diesel is less than 20 μm , whereas it is greater than 20 μm for blends.

According to a survey of the literature, significant research has been carried out to analyse the performance, emission, and combustion of various biodiesel blends and compression ratios, but there has been no research done to assess the performance, emission, and combustion of hibiscus *cocos nucifera* (HCN) methyl ester. As a result, it is critical to investigate the performance, combustion and emission characteristics of HCN biodiesel in a diesel engine. The current research compares the performance, emission, and combustion characteristics of HCN biodiesel blend B25 to diesel. At different loads, the performance, emission, and combustion characteristics such as brake thermal efficiency (BTE), brake specific fuel consumption (BSFC), carbon dioxide (CO_2), hydrocarbon (HC), smoke, cylinder pressure (CP), cumulative heat release (CHR), net heat release rate (NHR), and mean gas temperature (MGT) are investigated at various compression ratios (15, 16, 17, and 18), and the results are compared with diesel at standard compression ratio 17.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Biodiesel preparation

The raw components for hibiscus *cocos nucifera* oil were Hibiscus *Rosa sinensis* (both flowers and foliage), coconut oil, and curry leaves. Hibiscus belongs to the flowering plant family Malvaceae. It is available around the world. Curry leaves, also known as *Murraya koenigii*, have anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, nicotinic acid, and other chemicals found in abundance. Transesterification produces the biodiesel employed in this study from hibiscus *cocos nucifera* oil. The procedure of turning oil triglycerides into biodiesel in the presence of a catalyst and alcohol is known as transesterification [18]. A catalyst combination comprising hibiscus *cocos nucifera* oil, potassium hydroxide (KOH) and methanol is placed in a three-necked reactor chamber fitted with a condenser and thermometer. In the reactor, the total mixture is heated to 60°C for 2 hours while being continuously agitated with a stirring device. The entire solution was then transferred to a funnel for separation. After cooling, there are two layers visible, methyl ester on top and glycerin on the bottom. Remove the separating funnel from the glycerin and hibiscus *cocos nucifera* methyl ester. Hot water is used to wash the oil to remove any suspended soap particles before heating it to evaporate any remaining moisture. Finally, hibiscus *cocos nucifera* biodiesel is available for usage.

2.2. Fuel properties

Table 1 gives the properties of hibiscus cocos nucifera methyl ester. All properties are measured in accordance with ASTM standards. A hydrometer is used to measure fuel density. The closed cup Pensky Martens experimental setup is used to determine the flash and fire points temperatures of the test fuel. The calorific value (CV) of the test fuel was calculated using a bomb calorimeter. Fuel viscosity is determined using a Redwood viscometer.

Table 1: The properties of biodiesel and diesel

Parameter	Unit	Biodiesel	Diesel
Density	kg/m ³	862	829
Flash point	°C	93	52
Fire point	°C	103	54
Calorific value	kJ/kg°C	9688	42775
Viscosity	cSt	2.94	2.07

2.3. Experimental setup and methodology

Figure 1: VCR test engine

Figure 1 represents the photographic view of the VCR test engine setup. Experiments were executed in a 4 stroke, one - cylinder VCR diesel engine with a 1500 rpm speed and at various compression ratios. A crank angle encoder and a pressure sensor are used for combustion analysis. The engine is running at 1500 rpm. Experiments were carried out with diesel and a B25 blend at compression ratios of 15, 16, 17, and 18. Tests were conducted to investigate the performance, emission and combustion characteristics under various loads.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Performance characteristics

3.1.1 Brake thermal efficiency

Figure 2: BTE with load

Figure 5 depicts brake thermal efficiency (BTE) with different loads and compression ratios for biodiesel blend B25. Brake thermal efficiency improved with a rise in compression ratio and load for diesel and biodiesel due to reduced heat loss and an increase in the temperature of compressed air (Renish R. R. et al. 2022). The BTE of the B25 blend at CR15, CR16, CR17 and CR18 has grown by 23.63%, 23.81%, 24.43% and 24.53%, respectively. Diesel at standard compression ratio 17 has 23.33% of BTE. The BTE improved by 5.14% at CR18 at peak load compared with diesel.

3.1.2 Brake specific fuel consumption (BSFC):

Figure 3: BSFC with load

BSFC is defined as the ratio of fuel consumption to engine power. Figure 3 indicates the BSFC variation with load and compression ratio for blend B25 and diesel. Diesel and B25 BSFC values decrease as load rises. As the compression ratio rises, BSFC falls due to improved combustion, owing to the fact that biodiesel has an elevated oxygen content. The lowest result of BSFC for B25 blend was 4.58 kg/kW-hr, whereas for diesel it was 21.22 at standard compression ratio 17, which is 78.41% lower than diesel at no load condition. The BSFC of all fuels has been found to be a constant of 0.35 kg/kW-hr. At full load, B25 at CR 18 gave BSFC of 0.35 kg/k Whr, which is less than 5.71% lower than diesel. BSFC decreases as load increases, and heat loss is decreased at maximum load because of enhanced combustion and a lower rate of fuel flow [20].

3.2. Emission Characteristics

3.2.1. Hydrocarbon (HC):

Figure 4: Hydrocarbon emission with load

Figure 4 displays the hydrocarbon emissions of biodiesel blend B25 at different compression ratios. As the compression ratio increases, the HC emission decreases due to increased cylinder pressure, temperature, and better combustion at peak load. At higher compression ratios, biodiesel's higher oxygen content and quicker ignition delay significantly reduce HC emissions [21]. At compression ratios 15, 16, 17, and 18, the HC emissions for B25 are 28 ppm, 27 ppm, 25 ppm, and 23 ppm at peak load conditions, whereas HC emission for diesel is 29 ppm at standard compression ratio 17. B25 at CR18 reduces HC emissions by 20.68% as compared to diesel fuel. The oxygen presence of biodiesel promotes the oxidation process of HC during the air-fuel mixing. The HC emissions of diesel and B25 increase with load, which may be due to increased fuel consumption [22].

3.2.2. Carbon dioxide (CO₂):

Figure 5: Carbon dioxide with load

Figure 5 indicates the CO₂ emission tendency for biodiesel blend B25 at different compression ratios. Blend B25 emits more CO₂ than diesel with increasing CR. At CR15, CR16, CR17, and CR18, it was 4.5, 4.6, 4.8, and 4.9% for blend B25, respectively. The lowest CO₂ emissions for diesel were 4.1% at CR17. B25 emits 19.51% more CO₂ than diesel. The higher CO₂ emissions are due to improved combustion inside the engine cylinder because biodiesel has a higher oxygen content. Higher CO₂ emissions as comparison to CO emissions imply improved fuel combustion in an engine cylinder. CO₂ is harmful to the environment at a higher level, but less poisonous than CO, and plants also take CO₂ and produce oxygen through the photosynthesis process [23].

3.2.3. Smoke opacity:

Figure 6: Smoke opacity with load

During combustion, smoke is generated in the rich fuel zone. Improper fuel-air mixing causes smoke or soot to be emitted when burning does not occur at an optimum rate [24]. Figure 6 demonstrates the engine load variation on smoke opacity at different compression ratios. The smoke rises for diesel and B25 as the load increases. Smoke emissions lowered as the compression ratio rose. The smoke emissions for B25 at CR15, CR16, CR17, and CR18 were 20.8%, 17.8%, 15.8%, and 10.4% at full load. The maximum and minimum smoke emission values for diesel (CR17) and B25 at full load are 22.8 and 10.4, respectively. The blend B25 emits the least amount of smoke emissions. B25 had 54.38% lower smoke emissions than diesel.

3.3. Combustion Characteristics

3.3.1. Cylinder pressure (CP):

Figure 7: CP with crank angle

Figure 7 shows the effect of CP on crank angle for blend B25 at different compression ratios. The cylinder pressures for blend B25 at CR15, CR16, CR17, and CR18 are 52.49 bar, 53.45 bar, 53.01 bar, and 65.92 bar. The CP for diesel is 63.35 bar at the standard compression ratio of CR17. The maximum CP is obtained at 65.92 bar at a 371° crank angle for blend B25, which is 4.05% higher than diesel. [25] observed the influence of butanol on the CI engine at different compression ratios. At CR18, blends B20 and B40 have higher values compared with diesel because of smooth vaporization and improved air-fuel ratio mixing. [26] investigated whether B20 has a higher value of CP than diesel. The cylinder pressure improved as the compression ratio increased due to greater mixing of

air and fuel ratios and smooth vaporization. High cylinder temperatures with high compression ratios were achieved by enhanced fuel atomization and the use of additional fuel in premixed combustion.

3.1.2. Cumulative heat release (CHR):

Figure 8: CHR with crank angle

Figure 8 indicates the CHR with compression ratio for the blend of B25 and diesel at maximum load. The CHR for diesel at standard compression ratio 17 is 0.95 kJ, and for B25, it is 0.91 kJ at CR15, 0.92 kJ at CR16, 0.88 kJ at CR17, and 0.96 kJ, respectively. The highest CHR is obtained at 0.96 KJ at a 401^o crank angle for blend B25 (CR18), which is a 1.04% higher value compared with diesel at the standard compression ratio. [27] measured the combustion parameters of linseed biodiesel in a VCR diesel engine at various compression ratios and blends. CHR is higher when compared with diesel for B20 and B30 at CR18 due to more oxygen in biodiesel and a shortened ignition delay.

3.1.3. Net heat release (NHR):

Figure 9: NHR with crank angle

Figure 9 shows the net heat release variation with different compression ratios for the blend of B25 and diesel at the peak load of the engine. The early stage of NHR curve had a negative slope due to the commencement of fuel vaporization all over the ignition delay interval. The NHR for diesel at standard compression ratio 17 is 76.36 J/deg CA, and for B25, it is 76.08 J/deg CA at CR15, 73.77 J/deg CA at CR16, 68.66 J/deg CA at CR17, and 65.37 J/deg CA, respectively. The maximum NHR is obtained as 76.08 J/deg CA at a 363^o crank angle for B25 at CR15, which

is a 0.36% lower value compared with diesel at the standard compression ratio. The NHR lowers as the compression ratio rises for blend B25 because of the little ignition delay; the premixed charge combustion stage is reduced for B25 blend compared with diesel [28], [29].

3.1.5. Mean gas temperature (MGT):

Figure 10: MGT with crank angle

Figure 10 shows the influence of MGT with crank angle for B25 at various compression ratios at 100% load on the engine. The mean gas temperature for diesel is 1436.2°C at standard compression ratio 17, while for blend B25, it is 1357.37 °C at CR15, 1358.68 °C at CR16, 1272.54 °C at CR17, and 1428.12 °C at CR18. The mean gas temperature for blend B25 at CR 18 is 1428.12 °C, which is 0.56% lower than diesel. [30] observed the combustion parameters of WCO biodiesel. The mean gas temperature of diesel fuel is higher compared with biodiesel because diesel has a higher calorific value.

4. Conclusion

The VCR diesel engine performance, emission, and combustion parameters fuelled with hibiscus cocos nucifera biodiesel blend B25 at 100% load, different compression ratios, and 1500 rpm constant speed are explored. The results are compared with the standard compression ratio (CR17) for diesel fuel. The experimental inquiry yielded the following conclusions: Blend B25 enhanced brake thermal efficiency by 5.14% at CR18 compared to diesel; blend B25 at CR18 had brake-specific fuel consumption of 0.35 kg/kWhr, which was 5.71% lower than diesel; blend B25 at CR18 reduced hydrocarbon emissions by 20.68% as compared to diesel; the blend B25 at CR18 emits 19.51% more CO₂ than diesel; smoke emissions for B25 decreased by 54.38% when compared with diesel; the maximum cylinder pressure of blend B25 at CR18 is 65.92%, which is improved up to 4.05%, higher than diesel fuel; the maximum cumulative heat release for blend B25 at CR18 is improved up to 0.96%, which is 1.04% higher than diesel fuel; the net heat release of B25 blend and diesel is nearly equal. The NHR for blend B25 is 76.08 J/deg CA, which is 0.36% less than diesel. The mean gas temperatures of blend B25 and diesel are nearly equal. The MGT for blend B25 at CR18 is 1428.12°C, which is 0.56% lower than diesel. Based on the data and conclusions, it is proposed that HCN biodiesel blend B25 can be put to effective use at a CR of 18:1 without engine modification.

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References

- [1] Manikandan G, Prabakaran R, Dhamodharan P, Kim SC, Joshuva GG, Boopathi M, Jegadheesan C. Performance analysis of a diesel engine using margosa oil ethyl ester-based biodiesel with diethyl ether as an oxygenated additive. *Case Studies in Thermal Engineering*. 2023 Oct 1;50:103496.
- [2] Mahian O, Bellos E, Markides CN, Taylor RA, Alagumalai A, Yang L, Qin C, Lee BJ, Ahmadi G, Safaei MR, Wongwises S. Recent advances in using nanofluids in renewable energy systems and the environmental implications of their uptake. *Nano Energy*. 2021 Aug 1;86:106069.
- [3] Thangavelu S K, Arthanarisamy M. Experimental investigation on engine performance, emission, and combustion characteristics of a DI CI engine using tyre pyrolysis oil and diesel blends doped with nanoparticles. *Environmental Progress & Sustainable Energy*. 2020 Mar;39(2):e13321.

- [4] Zamba ZZ, Reshad AS. Synthesis of fatty acid methyl ester from Croton macrostachyus (bisana) kernel oil: parameter optimization, engine performance, and emission characteristics for Croton macrostachyus kernel oil fatty acid methyl ester blend with mineral diesel fuel. *ACS omega*. 2022 Jun 8;7(24):20619-33.
- [5] Rajak U, Verma TN. Influence of combustion and emission characteristics on a compression ignition engine from a different generation of biodiesel. *Engineering Science and Technology, an International Journal*. 2020 Feb 1;23(1):10-20.
- [6] Suresh M, Jawahar CP, Richard A. A review on biodiesel production, combustion, performance, and emission characteristics of non-edible oils in variable compression ratio diesel engine using biodiesel and its blends. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*. 2018 Sep 1;92:38-49.
- [7] Saravanan A, Murugan M, Reddy MS, Parida S. Performance and emission characteristics of variable compression ratio CI engine fueled with dual biodiesel blends of Rapeseed and Mahua. *Fuel*. 2020 Mar 1;263:116751.
- [8] Balasubramanian R, Subramanian KA. Experimental investigation on the effects of compression ratio on performance, emissions and combustion characteristics of a biodiesel-fueled automotive diesel engine. *Biofuels*. 2021 Sep 14.
- [9] Soni AK, Kumar S, Pandey M. Performance comparison of microalgae biodiesel blends with petro–diesel on variable compression ratio engine. *Journal of The Institution of Engineers (India): Series E*. 2020 Oct:1-1.
- [10] Babji A, Govada R, Balaji ND. Experimental investigations into engine characteristics fuelled with hibiscus coconut biodiesel and its blends. *International Journal of Advanced Technology and Engineering Exploration*. 2023;10(98):139.
- [11] Kabudke PD, Kharde YR, Parkhe RA. Experimental investigation on performance of cotton seed biofuel blended with diesel on variable compression ratio diesel engine. *Materials Today: Proceedings*. 2023 Jan 1;72:846-52.
- [12] Tamilselvan R, Periyasamy S. A novel investigation in the performance, combustion and emission characteristics of variable compression ratio engine using bio-diesel blends. *Journal of Mechanical Science and Technology*. 2022 Apr;36(4):1729-38.
- [13] Babji A, Rambabu G, Dhanavath BN, Cheworei LP, Rao DS. Optimization of Compression Ignition Diesel Engine Combustion, Emission, and Performance Characteristics at Higher Blends of Biodiesel Using RSM. *Process Integration and Optimization for Sustainability*. 2024 Mar 20:1-21.
- [14] Gultekin N, Ciniviz M. Experimental investigation of the effects of energy ratio and combustion chamber design on engine performance and emissions in a hydrogen-diesel dual-fuel CRDI engine. *Atmospheric Pollution Research*. 2024 Jun 19:102235.
- [15] Dash SK, Lingfa P, Chavan SB. Combustion analysis of a single cylinder variable compression ratio small size agricultural DI diesel engine run by Nahar biodiesel and its diesel blends. *Energy Sources, Part A: Recovery, Utilization, and Environmental Effects*. 2020 Jul 17;42(14):1681-90.
- [16] Rajendran R, Venkatachalapathy V, Velmurugan K, Elangovan M, Balu P. Study on exhaust gas recirculation diesel engine using karanja oil methyl ester with low heat rejection in direct injection. *Journal of Thermal Engineering*. 2024 Mar 1;10(2):396-403.
- [17] Chandrashekar R. Comparative analysis of carbon particle emissions from exhaust of an IC engine using HSD and blends of HSD and Honge/Jatropha biodiesel. *Journal of Thermal Engineering*. 2023 Jul 1;9(4):1070-7.
- [18] Elwardany AE, Marei MN, Eldrainy Y, Ali RM, Ismail M, El-Kassaby MM. Improving performance and emissions characteristics of compression ignition engine: Effect of ferrocene nanoparticles to diesel-biodiesel blend. *Fuel*. 2020 Jun 15;270:117574.
- [19] Renish RR, Selvam AJ, Čep R, Elangovan M. Influence of varying compression ratio of a compression ignition engine fueled with B20 blends of sea mango biodiesel. *Processes*. 2022 Jul 21;10(7):1423.
- [20] Baweja S, Trehan A, Kumar R. Combustion, performance, and emission analysis of a CI engine fueled with mustard oil biodiesel blended in diesel fuel. *Fuel*. 2021 May 15;292:120346.
- [21] Sivaramkrishnan K. Investigation on performance and emission characteristics of a variable compression multi fuel engine fuelled with Karanja biodiesel–diesel blend. *Egyptian Journal of Petroleum*. 2018 Jun 1;27(2):177-86.

- [22] Chand SM, Prakash JO, Rohit K. Impact of biodiesel blends on performance, emissions and waste heat recovery of diesel engine driven cogeneration system. *Journal of Thermal Engineering*. 2021;10(3):680-96.
- [23] Dugala NS, Goindi GS, Sharma A. Experimental investigations on the performance and emissions characteristics of dual biodiesel blends on a varying compression ratio diesel engine. *SN Applied Sciences*. 2021 Jun;3(6):622.
- [24] Rama Krishna Reddy E, Subbalakshmi Y, Dhana Raju V, Appa Rao K, Harun Kumar M, Rami Reddy S, Tharun Sai P. Assessment of performance, combustion and emission characteristics of the diesel engine powered with corn biodiesel blends. *International Journal of Ambient Energy*. 2022 Dec 31;43(1):435-43.
- [25] Prasad KS, Rao SS, Raju VR. Effect of compression ratio and fuel injection pressure on the characteristics of a CI engine operating with butanol/diesel blends. *Alexandria Engineering Journal*. 2021 Feb 1;60(1):1183-97.
- [26] Karami R, Rasul MG, Khan MM, Salahi MM, Anwar M. Experimental and computational analysis of combustion characteristics of a diesel engine fueled with diesel-tomato seed oil biodiesel blends. *Fuel*. 2021 Feb 1;285:119243.
- [27] Warkhade GS, Babu AV. Combustion characteristics of linseed (*Linum usitatissimum*) methyl ester fuelled biodiesel blends in variable compression ratio diesel engine. *Australian Journal of Mechanical Engineering*. 2019 Jan 2;17(1):38-51.
- [28] Mubarak M, Shaija A, Suchithra TV. Experimental evaluation of *Salvinia molesta* oil biodiesel/diesel blends fuel on combustion, performance and emission analysis of diesel engine. *Fuel*. 2021 Mar 1;287:119526.
- [29] Sun C, Liu Y, Qiao X, Ju D, Tang Q, Fang X, Zhou F. Experimental study of effects of exhaust gas recirculation on combustion, performance, and emissions of DME-biodiesel fueled engine. *Energy*. 2020 Apr 15;197:117233.
- [30] Mohamed M, Tan CK, Fouda A, Gad MS, Abu-Elyazeed O, Hashem AF. Diesel engine performance, emissions and combustion characteristics of biodiesel and its blends derived from catalytic pyrolysis of waste cooking oil. *Energies*. 2020 Oct 31;13(21):5708.